

WHAT IS NLP?

With the increasing amount of environmental research, natural language processing (NLP) methods can assist in gathering and organizing evidence

TIME-SAVER

NLP can help categorize documents by their subjects, find gaps in knowledge, create databases, and identify connections between ideas

AUTOMATION

In 66% of cases, NLP accurately identified the relationships described in abstracts, such as whether the impact of tillage on yield was positive, neutral, or negative

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AUTHORS

Guillaume Blanchy, Lukas Albrecht, John Koestel, Sarah Garré (2023)

EMPOWERING ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH: NLP FOR METADATA EXTRACTION

Opportunities

While the NLP techniques discussed in this study cannot replace human intervention, their automatic nature enables us to quickly process a large corpus of scientific publications.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT CLIMASOMA

The aim of project Climasoma is to contribute to an alignment of research strategies connecting agricultural management, soil quality and climate adaptation potential through its summary of the literature, its meta-analysis and its identification of knowledge gaps.

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation, **sustainable agricultural production and environment.**

Mission SOIL: conserve soil organic carbon stocks.

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
CLIMASOMA

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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